

Parallel GNN-LSTM Model Predicting Working Memory Involvement during Language and Emotion Processing

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Abstract

Working memory (WM) is a core cognitive system, strongly associated with the prefrontal cortex (PFC), crucial for task-relevant information storage and processing, serving as the main “relay” for higher cognition. Although WM-specific n-back tasks are examined, their measurable involvement in other cognitive processes remains less explored using computational models. Here, we developed and suggested a parallel GNN-LSTM model trained on WM task-fMRI data to predict its involvement in unseen language and emotion tasks. Integrating spatial and temporal information, the proposed GNN-LSTM model effectively learnt WM demand patterns and predicted WM demand when presented with non-WM task-fMRI data. As both the preliminary MLP and the GNN-LSTM models achieved over 90% accuracy, our approach was capable of generating a probability-based output corresponding to task demand and WM involvement, especially in language subtasks, math and story. This demonstration of cross-domain prediction, using WM signatures to create a “sensor” of cognitive demand alongside the model-based insights, offers a potential method for investigating cognitive resource allocation and informs the data-driven verification of WM theories..

Introduction

Working memory (WM) is a critical cognitive system responsible for the active and flexible maintenance and manipulation of task-relevant information, essential for guiding complex, goal-directed behaviours (Baddeley, 2003; Cowan, 2010; Eriksson et al., 2015; Stokes, 2015). As a key component of cognitive control, WM underpins a wide range of high-level cognitive functions (Baddeley, 2012; Miller & Cohen, 2001; Whitehead et al., 2019). Despite extensive research, its neural architecture remains debated. The cognitive perspective conceptualizes WM as a multi-component model, highlighting a centralized architecture (Baddeley et al., 2020), comprising four distinct, functionally specialized subsystems: the phonological loop, visuospatial sketchpad, central executive, and episodic buffer, managing and processing information inputs (Baddeley & Hitch, 1974; Baddeley, 2000). Within this framework, cognitive control and resource allocation are attributed to the central executive, which coordinates the other three subsystems. Neuroimaging findings support this model, implicating the PFC in executive control, the parietal cortex in storing and retrieving specialized information, and the occipital cortex in maintaining visual information (Baddeley, 2003).

In contrast, from a neurobiological perspective, WM relies on dynamic, distributed interactions across the cortical and subcortical regions (Bays, 2014). This dynamic neural resources (DyNR) model argues for the continuous and distributed allocation of neural resources, suggesting that WM representations emerge from dynamic interactions across a network of regions, with resource allocation flexibility adapting to task demands. Research from verbal and sensory WM tasks has supported this view (Embury et al., 2019; Tomić &

Bays, 2024), suggesting that the dynamic nature of neural resource allocation underlies the precision of WM representations.

Beyond its core functions, WM interacts critically with other cognitive domains such as language and emotion processing. Language tasks demand robust WM resources to support complex syntactic and semantic operations (Nakamura & Rossi, 2025). The interaction between WM and language involves subcortical structures and widespread right hemispheric regions (Deldar et al., 2020). Similarly, the WM-Emotion interaction involves the prefrontal and subcortical regions, including the amygdala, with PFC modulating emotional responses to ensure that emotionally charged information is appropriately weighted without overwhelming WM capacity (Grimm et al., 2012; Lopez-Franco et al., 2018).

However, investigations into these interactions typically manipulated stimuli within WM tasks, e.g., using emotionally-charged stimuli within an n-back task. While crucial for understanding these content-specific interactions and the role of WM in handling different inputs, this approach primarily illuminates the interplay at the task-specific level. Consequently, it may be less equipped for addressing more fundamental questions about whether the underlying mechanisms of WM representations are shared across distinct cognitive domains. A new approach is therefore needed to assess generalized WM involvement in high-level cognition that is not explicitly designed to probe WM.

The study proposed a computational approach using fMRI data to infer the level of WM involvement during other cognitive tasks. A simpler Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) model was first built to classify WM demand from fMRI signals and to assess the feasibility of training a computational model on WM task data for predictions on Emotion and Language tasks. We

then trained a parallel Graph Neural Network (GNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model to learn neural patterns associated with varying levels of cognitive demand (high vs. low) within standard n-back tasks. The trained models were then applied to language and emotion task data to predict the probability of high WM demand engagement, thereby testing for cross-domain generalization of the learnt patterns.

Methods

Data Acquisition

Task-based fMRI data from a 100-subject subset of the Human Connectome Project (HCP) Young Adult were obtained from NMA through OSF (Mineault et al., 2024). Subject-wise DataFrames containing parcel-based BOLD timeseries were created by extracting data from target experiments: WM (subtasks: Body, Faces, Places, Tools; conditions: 0-back, 2-back), Emotion (Neutral, Fear), and Language (Story, Math).

Working Memory Demand (WMD) Model

For the preliminary model, WM timeseries of 0-back (low demand) and 2-back (high demand) conditions were processed by averaging the exposure-wise BOLD signals across time points. These averaged data were aggregated into a single DataFrame, where exposures were labeled as 0 (0-back) or 1 (2-back) and used to train the model after an exposure-wise train-test split. The Emotion and Language data were processed using the same pipeline, with the exception of labelling.

The WMD model, containing four dense and dropout (rate = 50%) layers, was arranged in a funnel shape to ensure feature extraction (*Fig.1, A-1*). The input to the model consisted of a single exposure from one subject in the previously constructed DataFrame of average BOLD

signals. The model outputs probability values between 0 and 1, corresponding to the probability that the exposure is considered a 0-back (low WM demand) task or a 2-back (high WM demand) task.

Working Memory Architecture and Demand (WMAD) Model

The WMAD model incorporated both spatial and temporal features of fMRI data using a parallel architecture of a GAT-LSTM; their outputs were fused and passed to an MLP classifier (*Fig.1, B-1*). Each subject's data was processed to create three matrices: 360x360 adjacency matrices (*Supp Fig.1*), parcel-based fMRI timeseries matrices, and target matrices consisting of integer labels for each subtask of the experiments. The data was first split by subject to create train and test sets. The train set was split again into train and validation sets. The Emotion and Language data were processed using the same pipeline, with the exception of creating target matrices.

In the WMAD model, the GAT received the adjacency and the parcel-based fMRI timeseries matrices, capturing network-level spatial features. In parallel, the LSTM component received the target and parcel-based fMRI timeseries matrices, processing the temporal sequence of dynamic activity across brain regions. The embeddings generated by the GAT and LSTM were then combined by the fusion layer, which generated the input for the MLP classifier. This MLP outputs a pair of probability values between 0 and 1, showing the likelihood of the input task corresponding to low and high WM demand.

Output Visualizations

Predictions generated by these models were filtered, and those corresponding to the 2-back subtask (high-demand) were visualized using Seaborn and Matplotlib. The filtration was

applied to allow for comparisons based only on the high-demand predictions. For the WMD model, predictions of Emotion and Language subtasks were plotted in a 3D histogram. For the WMAD model, the probability of high WM demand for each parcel was isolated, and parcel-wise predictions were visualized separately for Emotion and Language subtasks in 3D histograms, showing the distribution of predicted WM involvement across brain regions.

Results

The WMD was trained for 50 epochs and achieved 90% accuracy when classifying the demands of WM tasks after half the training (*Fig.1, A-2*). When exposed to the Emotion and Language subtasks, the model predicted Math as exhibiting high WM involvement, while predicting the Fear and Story tasks as having low WM involvement. The neutral task did not consistently fall into either category (*Fig.1, C-1*).

The WMAD was trained on the WM tasks with early stopping based on validation loss, for a maximum of 50 epochs. The GNN-LSTM-MLP structure achieved 100% accuracy on the WM-demand classification task with 0% validation loss after 5 epochs (*Fig.1, B-2*). WMAD provided similar predictions on Language tasks, with a high involvement of WM in the Math task and a low WM involvement in the Story task. However, unlike the WMD model, the WMAD model predicted the Fear task requiring high WM resources. The Neutral task, again, showed ambiguous predictions (*Fig.1, C-2*).

Discussion

Our study demonstrated the feasibility of predicting cognitive demand based on WM-trained models across domains. Specifically, our cross-domain approach successfully generalized to predict WM involvement in the Math subtask. Consistent with previous expectations

(Arsalidou & Taylor, 2011), the models identified the Math subtask as high WM demand, reflecting substantial cognitive resource requirements. However, the Story subtask, predicted as low demand, likely reflects lower WM requirements for passive listening, where participants only needed to track the narrative for comprehension checks rather than recall details in the story, aligning with previous studies (Evelyn et al., 2008). In contrast to the Language experiments, Emotion predictions were less clear. This may stem from the prominent role of subcortical regions, like the amygdala, in processing Fear (Nummenmaa, 2021; Supp Fig. 2-C, 2-D). The neural demand signatures learned from cortically-dominant WM experiments might not directly map onto emotion-processing circuits.

Several limitations should be considered. Mainly, the WMAD model exhibited potential signs of overfitting, possibly due to the sample size and model structure, which could be tested using other datasets. Furthermore, our current pipeline disregarded sensory modalities of cognitive tasks (e.g., visual vs. auditory inputs) that could influence WM-related activation and generated outputs. Moreover, the scope of model generalizability was limited to the Emotion and Language experiments; testing the model on other cognitive tasks from HCP or other datasets could provide more comprehensive model assessments.

The WMAD model, featuring a parallel GNN-LSTM and an MLP, contributes to investigations of fMRI-based cognitive demand predictions. While GNN-LSTMs have been used in a parallel manner (Tang et al., 2024), their use with fMRI data for predicting WM involvement has not been explored. With graph-based functional connectivity and parcel-wise temporal dynamics, the proposed model has shown potential in identifying a domain-general pattern of brain activity related to WM activation and predicting WM demand in unseen cognitive domains.

While cognitive states cannot be solely predicted from fMRI data, insights from our models significantly advance data-driven understanding of cognitive resource allocation in high-level cognition and potentially offer a new pathway for empirically verifying the theories of WM architecture. Building on this work, future research should aim to address current limitations and explore shared WM demand signatures through the incorporation of larger datasets and diverse cognitive tasks. Furthermore, we should move towards a deeper understanding of neural representation transformations and cross-regional information flow during WM tasks, which provides insights into cognitive resource allocation mechanisms. In conclusion, this study provides proof of concept for classifying cross-domain neural patterns to investigate WM demand, opening new paths to explore neural representations of human cognition.

A. Working Memory Demand (WMD) Model

A-1. WMD Model Structure

A-2. WMD Accuracy

B. Working Memory Architecture and Demand (WMAD) Model

B-1. WMAD Model Structure

B-2. WMAD Accuracy

C. WMD and WMAD Results

C-1. WMD Results

C-2. WMAD Results

Figure 1. From parcel-based BOLD signals to predictions

A. WMD Model: A-1. An MLP with a funnel-shaped structure takes in average parcel-based BOLD signals. A-2. The WMD achieved an accuracy of 90%.

B. WMAD Model: B-1. Subject-based adjacency matrices, parcel-based BOLD timeseries, and target matrices are input into the GAT and the LSTM. Outputs are unified through the fusion layer and passed to an MLP to generate the final parcel-based demand probability. B-2. A 100% accuracy for WMAD, possibly due to overfitting or data sparsity.

C. WMD and WMAD results: C-1. WMD predicts math as high-demand, fear and story as low-demand, and does not predict neutral subtask in either category. C-2. WMAD shows similar predictions for math, story, and neutral subtask, but predicts fear as high-demand (C-2, top left).

Abbreviations

Blood-oxygen-level-dependant (BOLD) signal, Dynamic Neural Resources (DyNR), Graph Attention Network (GAT), Graph Neural Network (GNN), Human Connectome Project (HCP), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), Prefrontal Cortex (PFC), Working Memory (WM), Working Memory Architecture and Demand (WMAD), Working Memory Demand (WMD)

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Code Availability

All Python notebooks, requirements, packages, figures, and, for those looking to use pretrained models, the saved model states are available in our project repository at https://github.com/saamehsanaaee/WMAD-Montbretia_Cabinet-ISP.

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Average Adjacency Matrix

(Constructed using working memory data of the 100 subject subset)

Supplementary Figure 1. Average Adjacency Matrix: Subject-wise adjacency matrices were constructed based on working memory task fMRI BOLD timeseries. These matrices were then averaged across subjects and the average adjacency matrix was plotted with a threshold of $> |0.25|$ for the correlation scores.

Reference activation for Working Memory, Language, Fear, and Neutral tasks
from the Neurosynth meta-analyses

A. Working memory Glass Brain

B. Language Glass Brain

C. Fear Glass Brain

D. Neutral Glass Brain

Supplementary Figure 2. Reference fMRI Activation

Reference activation maps for the available subtasks were obtained using the meta-analysis association data provided by Neurosynth and visualized on a Glass Brain using the Nilearn and Brainspace packages.